

WAYS TO OVERCOME STRESS SITUATIONS IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

The formation of a comprehensively developed, harmoniously developed generation is one of the priorities of state policy. One of the main tasks of the education system is to train competitive personnel in line with world standards. At all levels of the education system, great attention is paid to the education of the younger generation, their social protection. In this regard, the study of problems related to the educational activities of students, who are the main subject of the higher education system, is also a requirement of the time.

In recent years, the issue of mental health of young people has become one of the research areas of psychology. In particular, the study of the negative processes observed in the psyche of the student and their negative impact on the effectiveness of education is becoming one of the important problems. One such problem is the stress observed in student youth, and there is a need to study in detail its impact on student learning activities. The urgency of this problem can be explained as follows: today young people are required to keep pace with the times.

While today's student has achieved a number of successes in the process of striving for economic, spiritual, ideological, religious, and professional maturity, it is natural that he or she will face specific challenges and stressogenic effects. In this process, it can be seen that a specific state of stress is observed in most students as a result of various factors.

Social aspects of studying stress

This concept is already firmly entrenched in our daily lives, but we use the word only in a negative sense. Stress is not always a damaging condition, but it is clear that it is necessary at times, as it helps to overcome obstacles and avoid danger.

Gans Sele, the author of the theory of stress, considered stress to be a non-specific response of the body to any demand presented to it. That is, stress is a universal reaction of our brain and body, which helps to overcome any obstacles: diseases, various tests, serve as the main criterion in the process of examinations [1].

Stresses and changes that cause stress offer two opportunities for a person: 1) to adapt to new living conditions; 2) helps to get out of potentially dangerous situations for people.

Of course, just as every problem has a solution, so can stress. Let's look at some of them.

Relaxation gymnastics.

Relaxation gymnastics (relaxation) is a method of physical exposure to muscle tone to relieve increased neuropsychotic tension, balance emotional state, and improve calmness and mood. In some sports, it is widely used to relieve nervous and emotional overload of athletes before competitions, reduce fatigue at work, and prevent stress. The origin of modern recreational gymnastics complexes is mainly associated with the development of yoga, kung fu. Relief can be achieved with the help of autosuggestion, special exercises, chemotherapeutic agents, but no matter what, it always occurs with a decrease in emotional arousal and an improvement in general condition.

The tension of certain muscle groups in the body occurs depending on the emotional nature. Throughout human life, psychological protection, that is, the protective mechanisms of the psyche, the protective mechanisms of the individual, traditionally appear and develop in the human psyche. With the help of defense mechanisms, a person unconsciously protects his psyche from negative situations.

Analyzing stress-related studies in recent years, it can be noted that most of them, in addition to studying the problem of stress, are studying its negative effects on the human body. In recent years, stress has become one of the main risk factors for human health, according to research conducted by most expert scientists. According to A.M. Wayne, who conducted research on this topic in the 1970s, "... the major diseases of our time occur under the influence of emotional stress" [2]. VK Sudakov, in one of his monographs on stress resilience, says: «... as a result of stress, a person develops psychosomatic diseases such as neurosis, heart failure, changes in blood pressure, ulcers in the gastrointestinal tract, immunodeficiency, endocrine system deficiencies and even tumors» [3].

Based on the above data, it can be said that the observation of somatic diseases caused by stress in young people in itself has a serious negative impact not only on the physical health but also on the mental health of modern students. As a result, the student's health problems may lead to a decrease in interest in studying or limited ability to continue academic activities. Such problems also have a serious negative impact on the effectiveness of education in the higher education system, which seeks to train competitive personnel.

To date, many scientists have conducted research on stress, and based on their data, it is noted that today there are two different types of stress according to their nature and characteristics. These are physiological and psychological stress, and physiological stress is the result of extreme levels of pain, fear, illness, and severe physical exertion. Psychological stress, on the other hand, occurs as a result of various mental tensions during attempts to deal with unexpected situations, and is divided into two types: information stress and emotional stress.

Information stress is caused by an excessive flow of information, a lack of time to assimilate them, or a lack of personal cognitive capacity in a person. The causes of emotional stress can be explained by the following: the subject works hard to perform the task assigned to him in the process of performing a certain activity, overloads himself, feels a high sense of responsibility in the process, makes the right decisions in solving and resolving situations

compression without being able to. Such factors occur in a state of overexertion that occurs for both the organism and the psyche.

The onset of physiological stress is caused by extreme levels of pain, fear, illness, and severe physical exertion. Psychological stress occurs as a result of various mental tensions during attempts to deal with unexpected situations, and it is divided into two types: informational stress and emotional stress.

The emergence of information stress is caused by factors such as excessive flow of information, lack of time to assimilate them, or lack of personal cognitive capabilities of the individual.

Emotional stress occurs in threats, dangers, frustrations, and other situations. In this case, its various forms (impulsive, inhibitory, diffuse) can lead to changes in mental processes, emotional arousal, motivational shifts in the structure of activity, the occurrence of disorders in movement and speech, as well as behavior. While stress can be positive, mobilizing, it can also have a negative effect on activity, i.e., distress. Therefore, to optimize any type of activity, it is necessary to develop a set of pre-warning measures about the causes of stress.

Psychological stress is always considered to be the result of a physiological adaptation mechanism in the human body, while biological mechanisms have their own specific nature and content. Without clarifying the understanding of these two mechanisms, it is impossible to explain the complex and contradictory nature of human reactions to stressful influences.

G. Sele's work «The stress of life», which includes many years of observations, is recognized as one of the first major works in this field. Author «Stress, perhaps, is not synonymous with distress?» [4] (Distress is an English word meaning sadness, unhappiness, lethargy, weight loss, need; increased stress, pressure, tension). Perhaps it can be stress, fatigue, exhaustion, pain, fear, discrimination by many, or, conversely, an unexpectedly great achievement that can drastically change your entire life.

The course of stress is systemic and includes the following factors:

1. Stressogenic event assessment;
2. Physiological and biochemical reaction to the event itself or its assessment;
3. Actions aimed at overcoming the causes and consequences of stress, behavioral reactions.

Conclusion. The most important thing is how the event is evaluated. The more unfair, excessive, and intolerable the event or event that is affecting the occurrence of stress, the more the sense of stress is felt. A person's firm belief in their own failure is also one of the factors that triggers stress. Hence, the initial reaction to stress is an assessment, which is always an individual's reaction, not an organism's.

The physiological and biological reactions in the second system of stress manifestations are given not spontaneously, but through the individual's perception and evaluation of the event; it is at this time that the unity of spirit and body emerges. The effect of the influencing factor on the organism is also felt.

The third system is the emotional and behavioral responses to the passage of stress. A person expresses how much he or she feels stress through his or her behavior.

It turns out that the psychological, physiological and biochemical responses of a person to stress are interrelated. At the same time, behind them is a "management team"; this management represents our attitude to life and the demands of life.

The concepts analyzed above show that stress (stress, nervous tension) states depend on a complex relationship of socio-psychological, situational and personal factors. In addition, it helps to more broadly identify the causes of stress and, consequently, to develop measures to prevent this condition.

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